

FREQUENCY OF SILENT CAROTID ARTERY STENOSIS AMONG PATIENTS WITH DIABETES PRESENTING AT MARDAN MEDICAL COMPLEX: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Objective:

To determine the frequency of silent carotid artery stenosis (CAS) among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and to assess its association with demographic and clinical factors.

Study Design and Setting:

Cross-sectional study conducted at the Department of General Medicine, Mardan Medical Complex, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Methodology:

A total of 187 patients aged 27–70 years with type 2 diabetes mellitus were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling over six months. All participants underwent bilateral carotid Doppler ultrasonography. Silent CAS was defined as $\geq 50\%$ stenosis without neurological symptoms. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27, and associations were assessed using the Chi-square test, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results:

The mean age of participants was 51.7 ± 8.3 years, with 53.5% males. Hypertension and smoking were present in 57.8% and 21.9% of patients, respectively. The overall frequency of silent CAS was 15.0%. Right-sided stenosis was observed in 8.0%, left-sided in 1.6%, and bilateral stenosis in 5.3% of patients. No significant association was found between silent CAS and age, gender, BMI, duration of diabetes, hypertension, smoking, socioeconomic status, education, or occupation ($p > 0.05$). A significant association was observed with place of residence, with higher prevalence among urban residents (19.6% vs. 8.0%, $p = 0.029$).

Conclusion:

Silent carotid artery stenosis is present in a notable proportion of asymptomatic diabetic patients. Urban residence was significantly associated with CAS. Targeted screening may help in early detection and prevention of cerebrovascular complications.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is one of the major global public health concern contributing to cardiovascular morbidity and mortality¹, its prevalence is continuously increasing, and the recent data indicated that more than 537 million adults worldwide are living with diabetes, and the number is expected to exceed 634 million by 2030²⁻⁴. Diabetes is having microvascular and macrovascular complications, the macrovascular complications of the diabetes are coronary artery disease, cerebrovascular disease and peripheral arterial disease^{5,6}. Diabetic patients have increased risk of developing atherosclerosis as compared to general population, due to endothelial dysfunction, chronic hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, chronic hyperglycemia all of these factors can increase vascular injury and plaque formation⁷⁻⁹.

Carotid artery stenosis (CAS) is one of the critical manifestation of systemic atherosclerosis and is a w risk factor for ischemic stroke¹⁰. Globally, approximately 10-20% of ischemic strokes are attributed to significant CAS, and the prevalence is rising with aging populations and increasing rates of diabetes^{11,12}. Most of the CAS cases remain asymptomatic called as silent carotid artery stenosis, in which significant arterial narrowing is present without preceding transient ischemic attack or stroke. These silent CAS carries an increased risk of future cerebrovascular events in individuals with risk factors such as hypertension, smoking, dyslipidemia and long-standing diabetes^{13,14}. Early detection and timely management with endarterectomy or stenting can substantially reduce stroke risk¹⁵.

Data from the previous literature has demonstrated higher prevalence of CAS in diabetic patients as compared to non-diabetic¹⁶. The studies from Europe, middle east and east asia reported CAS prevalence ranging from 15-35% in diabetic patients, and the risk is increasing with age, poor glycemic control and duration of diabetes^{17,18}. Regional data from south asia also revealed a significant burden of asymptomatic carotid atherosclerosis among diabetic, the finding is variable across different studies due to differences in population characteristics, health

care access and diagnostic approach used^{17,19}. In Pakistan there are limited studies on the epidemiology of CAS among diabetic patients, there is lack of evidence from the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province including Mardan, where the diabetic prevalence is increasing and the cardiovascular risk profiles is different from other parts of the county.

This lack of availability of local data creates a critical knowledge gap, as these patients remain undiagnosed until a major cardiovascular event occurs. Understanding the frequency of silent CAS in this high-risk population is essential, it will inform clinicians in screening strategies, timely diagnosis and clinical decision making.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a cross-sectional study conducted at the department of general medicine Mardan medical complex, which is a tertiary care hospital of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa serving a large population of Mardan and surrounding areas of Mardan Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan, the study duration was six months from July 2024 to December 2024. The study included adults, male and female, aged 27 to 70 years, with a confirmed diagnosis of diabetes mellitus (individuals with HbA1c \geq 6.5% or random blood glucose \geq 200 mg/dL). The sampling technique was consecutive sampling, and patients were enrolled consecutively as they presented to the outpatient department. The exclusion criteria were patients with having a history of stroke or transient ischemic attack, having a previous history of carotid artery stenosis, prior stenting or carotid artery endarterectomy, neck mass or enlarged cervical lymph nodes, or any other condition that compromises adequate Doppler assessment.

Silent CAS was defined as \geq 50% narrowing of the carotid artery in the absence of retinal or cerebral ischemic symptoms. The sample size was 187, which was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator based on a previously reported prevalence of silent CAS of 28.92% among diabetic individuals, the confidence level was 95% and the margin of error was 6.5% margin of error. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and data were collected on a

structured proforma, which included demographic and clinical information such as age, Body mass index, sex, smoking status, hypertension, duration of diabetes, socioeconomic status, education level, and area of residence was recorded. All participants underwent bilateral carotid Doppler ultrasonography performed in the Radiology Department of Mardan Medical Complex by an experienced Radiologist using a high-resolution B-mode ultrasound machine equipped with a 7-12 MHz linear transducer. Standard Doppler criteria were used for evaluating the stenosis; the standard criteria included peak systolic velocity (PSV), end-diastolic velocity (EDV), and the internal carotid artery to common carotid artery (ICA/CCA) PSV ratio. A PSV ≥ 125 cm/s or an ICA/CCA ratio ≥ 2.0 was taken as indicative of $\geq 50\%$ stenosis. The dependent variable of the study was the presence of silent carotid artery stenosis, defined as $\geq 50\%$ stenosis on Doppler ultrasonography without neurological symptoms. Independent variables of the study were age, gender, BMI, duration of diabetes, smoking status, hypertension, occupation, education status, socioeconomic category, and residence. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Review Committee of Mardan Medical Complex and Bacha Khan Medical College, ethical approval number 507/BKMC, dated 24/05/2024.

Data analysis was done using IBM SPSS Statistics version 27; all the continuous variables, such as

age, BMI, and duration of diabetes, were summarized as \pm standard deviation (SD), and categorical variables, such as gender, smoking status, hypertension, and presence of silent CAS, were presented as frequency and percentages. Silent CAS was stratified across demographic and clinical variables to evaluate potential effect modifiers. The Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was applied for the comparison of categorical variables, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Baseline characteristics of the study population

The study population comprised a total of 187 patients with diabetes. The mean age was 51.7 ± 8.3 years, and the mean BMI was 27.8 ± 5.2 kg/m². The mean duration of diabetes was 12.5 ± 5.7 years. The mean HbA1c level was $8.3 \pm 1.3\%$, while the mean random blood glucose was 227.4 ± 52.1 mg/dL. The mean right and left carotid peak systolic velocities were 86.9 ± 28.1 cm/s and 86.1 ± 24.3 cm/s, respectively.

More than half of the participants were male (53.5%). Hypertension was present in 57.8% of patients, and 21.9% were smokers. The majority of participants were literate (66.8%), and 56.7% were employed. Nearly half of the participants (47.1%) belonged to the lower socioeconomic class, while 59.9% resided in urban areas. Baseline characteristics are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of the Study Population (N = 187)

Variable	Frequency (%) or Mean \pm SD
Age (years)	51.7 ± 8.3
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.8 ± 5.2
Duration of diabetes (years)	12.5 ± 5.7
HbA1c (%)	8.33 ± 1.33
Random blood sugar (mg/dL)	227.4 ± 52.1
Right PSV (cm/s)	86.9 ± 28.1
Left PSV (cm/s)	86.1 ± 24.3
Gender	Male 100 (53.5%), Female 87 (46.5%)
Hypertension	Yes 108 (57.8%), No 79 (42.2%)

Variable	Frequency (%) or Mean ± SD
Smoking	Yes 41 (21.9%), No 146 (78.1%)
Education	Literate 125 (66.8%), Illiterate 62 (33.2%)
Occupation	Employed 106 (56.7%), Unemployed 81 (43.3%)
Socioeconomic status	Lower 88 (47.1%), Middle 77 (41.2%), Upper 22 (11.8%)
Residence	Urban 112 (59.9%), Rural 75 (40.1%)

Prevalence and laterality of silent carotid artery stenosis

The majority of patients had <50% stenosis of the right (86.6%) and left (93.0%) carotid arteries. Significant stenosis ≥50% was found on the right side in 13.4%, while it was found on the left side in only 7.0%. Silent carotid artery stenosis ≥50% without any neurological symptoms was found to

be present in 28 patients, giving an overall prevalence of 15.0% in this diabetic population. Of these, 8.0% of patients had isolated right-sided stenosis, while 1.6% of patients had isolated left-sided stenosis. Another 5.3% of patients had bilateral stenosis. This detail is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Prevalence and Laterality of Silent Carotid Artery Stenosis

Variable	Frequency (%)
Silent CAS (overall)	28 (15.0%)
No Silent CAS	159 (85.0%)
Right-sided silent CAS	15 (8.0%)
Left-sided silent CAS	3 (1.6%)
Bilateral silent CAS	10 (5.3%)

Association of silent CAS with demographic and clinical variables

Silent CAS showed no statistically significant association with age group ($p=0.539$), gender ($p=0.689$), BMI category ($p=0.519$), duration of diabetes ($p=0.617$), hypertension status ($p=0.627$), smoking ($p=0.357$), socioeconomic status ($p=0.753$), education level ($p=0.153$), or occupational status ($p=0.439$).

However, a significant association was observed between place of residence and silent CAS, with a higher prevalence among urban residents (19.6%) compared with rural residents (8.0%) ($p = 0.029$). All stratified analyses with corresponding chi-square p-values are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Association of Silent CAS with Demographic and Clinical Factors

Variable	Silent CAS (%)	p-value
Age group	26.7%, 26.7%, 46.7%	0.539
Gender	Male 14%, Female 16.1%	0.689
BMI category	Normal 25%, Overweight 32.1%, Obese 42.9%	0.519
Diabetes duration	4.2%, 25%, 70.8%	0.617
Hypertension	13.9% vs 16.5%	0.627
Smoking	19.5% vs 13.7%	0.357

Variable	Silent CAS (%)	p-value
Socioeconomic status	53.6%, 35.7%, 10.7%	0.753
Education	9.7% vs 17.6%	0.153
Occupation	50% vs 50%	0.439
Residence	Rural 8.0% vs Urban 19.6%	0.029 (significant)

DISCUSSION

The present study investigated the frequency and correlates of silent carotid artery stenosis (CAS) among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus presenting to a Mardan Medical Complex Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan. The overall prevalence of silent CAS in this cohort was 15%, indicating that a substantial proportion of asymptomatic diabetic individuals may harbor clinically significant carotid atherosclerosis. The prevalence of this study is lower compared to other international studies. De Angelis et al. reported a prevalence of 52.8% of carotid stenosis in Italian adults with type 2 diabetes. They concluded that diabetics are three times more likely to have stenosis compared to non-diabetics. Another study by Koroleva and Khapaev revealed a prevalence of 33.9% of CAS among 389 diabetic patients. The study concluded that the prevalence of CAS in Russia is significant. The population of this study may have a different age profile compared to other studies. The mean age of this study population was significantly lower compared to other studies. The mean age of our study population was 51.7 years, while the mean age of other studies was greater than 65 years. The progression of carotid stenosis depends on age. Young populations have lower stenosis rates even if they have diabetes²⁰²¹.

Regional variation of the prevalence of CAS in Pakistan has been reported. A study published in Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences revealed that the prevalence of silent CAS in diabetic patients of Pakistan was 28.9%, which is almost double that of our study²². Differences in referral pathways, inclusion criteria, and sonographic thresholds may contribute to the heterogeneity. The present study focused exclusively on asymptomatic individuals, whereas other Pakistani studies included patients with vascular symptoms or higher cardiovascular risk profiles.

Our results have shown that silent CAS has no significant association with classical risk factors. This finding, although unexpected, has been noted in some populations where there was no significant difference in carotid artery distribution among risk groups, especially among younger populations. However, various international studies have confirmed that age > 65 years, diabetes duration > 15 years, hypertension, renal dysfunction, and microvascular complications such as retinopathy are strong predictors for CAS^{18,19,21}. Koroleva et al. have emphasized that decreased eGFR, retinopathy, and myocardial infarction are significant risk factors for silent CAS. In another study published by Acta Diabetologica, silent vascular disease has been linked to male gender, hypertension, and dyslipidaemia^{19,23}. The difference between our study findings and international literature could be attributed to sample size differences rather than a lack of association. A significant association has been noted between urban residence and silent CAS. This is because South Asian populations living in urban environments have higher rates of cardiometabolic risk factors. This is because they are more prone to lifestyle changes, pollution, and psychosocial stress, which accelerate endothelial dysfunction and atherosclerosis. This finding has been supported by various regional studies that have shown that cardiovascular diseases are higher among urban populations.

The need to detect silent CAS among diabetics has been emphasized by various studies that have shown that silent carotid artery disease has been linked to neurological consequences. A systematic review and meta-analysis by Finn et al. have shown that carotid artery stenosis increases the risk of silent brain infarction 2.78-fold. This increases the risk of stroke twice¹³. These findings highlight the critical role of early detection of asymptomatic

carotid disease as part of comprehensive cerebrovascular risk reduction strategies in diabetic patients.

Our study has several strengths such as well-defined cohort, standardized Doppler ultrasonography, and a comprehensive assessment of clinical variables. There are certain limitations, such as a cross-sectional study design, single-centered, and younger mean age of the participants, which may limit the comparability to older diabetic cohorts having higher prevalence of stenosis. In addition to that the lack of plaque morphology assessment, inflammatory markers, and advanced imaging modalities may have underestimated early or nonobstructive carotid disease.

In conclusion, silent carotid artery stenosis is present in a substantial proportion of asymptomatic diabetic adults in Pakistan, with an overall prevalence of 15%. Although most traditional risk factors were not statistically associated with CAS in this cohort, urban residence emerged as a significant correlate. Given the strong international evidence linking asymptomatic carotid disease to stroke and cardiovascular events, selective screening of high-risk diabetic individuals, particularly older, urban, or long-standing diabetic patients, should be considered to facilitate early intervention and reduce vascular morbidity.

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Author Contributions

Dr. Azam Khan contributed to the conception and design of the study, data collection, statistical analysis, and drafting of the manuscript.

Dr. Naveed Khan supervised the study, contributed to study design, interpretation of data, and critically revised the manuscript for important intellectual content.

Dr. Muhammad Zaid contributed to data collection, literature review, and manuscript preparation.

Dr. Junaid Islam contributed to data collection, data analysis, and manuscript drafting.

Dr. Waleed Ahmad Khan contributed to data collection, literature review, and manuscript editing.

Dr. Waqar Ahmad contributed to data collection, interpretation of results, and final manuscript review.

All authors approved the final version of the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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